

EFFECTIVENESS OF HOMOEOPATHIC REMEDIES TO REDUCE THE USAGE OF PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS IN GASTRIC COMPLAINTS

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To assess the effectiveness of homoeopathic medicines in patients who are using Proton Pump Inhibitors(PPI) for gastric complaints. **Materials and methods:** A total of 30 patients, aged between 18 to 75 years, with gastric complaints and using PPIs 3-5 times/week for more than 4-8 weeks to reduce their symptoms were enrolled in the study. Patients attending, Bharati Vidyapeeth Medical Foundation Homoeopathic Hospital are enrolled. Constitutional medicine was prescribed after thorough case-taking and repertorization. Improvement assessment was based on the Gastro-Intestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) scale score and subjective relief in symptoms. The drug was administered in globule form orally. Repetition of dose was decided based on the assessment of the GIQLI score during the follow-up. **Results:** The GIQLI scores were analyzed before and after the treatment using a paired t-test. Before the treatment intervention, the average GIQLI score was 100.46 ± 11.21 (mean \pm SD); after the intervention, the average GIQLI score was 127.66 ± 9.99 (mean \pm SD). The t-statistic value was -14.68 and the significant p-value of 0.00* which concluded that there was a significant difference in the average GIQLI score, before and after treatment. Hence Homoeopathic medicines are effective in patients with gastric complaints who are on PPIs. Marked improvement is seen in 36.67% of the patients with Gastric complaints, 40% of patients showed a moderate improvement, whereas 20% had a mild improvement. Only 3.33% of patients had no improvement. Mean \pm standard deviation of the GIQLI score difference after and before the treatment. The average GIQLI score differences were 36.82 ± 5.13 for marked improvement, 26.75 ± 3.22 for moderate improvement, and 14.33 ± 3.44 for mild improvement. Homoeopathic medicines that were used in this study were Arsenicum Album, Bryonia, Argentum Nitricum, Lycopodium clavatum, Phosphorus, Pulsatilla and Nux Vomica. Among patients treated with Bryonia and Argentum nitricum, 75% had moderate improvement and 25% showed mild improvement. Among patients treated with pulsatilla Arsenicum album and Lycopodium, 66.7% had marked improvement, and 33.3% showed moderate improvement. When patients received Nux Vomica, 42.9% had marked improvement, 28.6% showed moderate improvement and 28.6% had mild improvement in gastric complaints. For patients treated with Phosphorus marked improvement is seen in 50%, 33.3% showed moderate improvement and mild improvement in 16.7%. Hence showing a significant difference between the symptom score which is taken before and after the treatment. The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was utilized to evaluate the hypothesis concerning symptom scores before and following treatment. and showed a significant difference. The test statistic for pain score was $Z = -4.615$ with a p-value of 0.00. Similarly, Bloating, Regurgitation and Heartburn scores before and after treatment were studied. Corresponding observed z-statistic values were -4.636, -4.934 and -4.05 respectively. The corresponding p-values were <0.01 , statistically highly significant. Based on these findings, indicates a significant improvement in symptom scores after treatment, enhancing patients' quality of life. **Conclusion:** Homoeopathic remedies have demonstrated substantial effectiveness in treating gastric symptoms, indicating that they are effective in patients with gastric complaints who are on PPIs.

Keywords:

Proton Pump Inhibitors, Gastritis, Peptic-Ulcer Disease, Rebound Acid Hypersecretion, Homoeopathy.

INTRODUCTION:

Homoeopathy is founded on the concept of "similia similibus curentur". Dr. Samuel Hahnemann, the founder of homoeopathy, gives it. This principle suggests that, when a material has the potential to cause symptoms in a healthy individual, it can also reduce those same symptoms in a diseased individual. According to Dr. Hahnemann, when medications are given in large doses, they aggravate the symptoms of the disease and worsen the condition. Still, when the same medicine is given in minimal doses, it triggers the vital force and cures the disease. Individualization is the core concept of homoeopathy, where the practitioners meticulously assess each patient's unique symptoms to identify the suitable homoeopathic remedy that is known for producing similar effects in healthy individuals. The homoeopathic approach to the treatment of patients involves matching the symptoms of the patient with the documented effects of the drugs. Once the similimum (the drug that is most similar to the patient's symptoms) is selected, the homoeopathic remedy is administered to the patient. These remedies undergo serial dilution and succussion (shaking) processes. This will potentize the remedies and enhance their effectiveness and therapeutic potency. ⁽¹⁾

Heartburn and indigestion are widespread health issues impacting a significant number of individuals. Concerns over the possible long-term effects of proton pump inhibitors have grown, as they are used for addressing gastrointestinal symptoms. In the patients taking PPI for unclear indications, discontinuation should be attempted. The abrupt PPI cessation can significantly increase gastric acid production, a condition referred to as rebound acid hypersecretion. As a result, this may exacerbate symptoms in the upper gastrointestinal tract. Studies indicate that forty per cent of healthy participants who stopped taking PPI after eight week's course experienced dyspepsia within the next four weeks. The severity of symptoms post-PPI discontinuation has been significantly associated with the level of hypergastrinemia induced by the PPI treatment. ⁽²⁾

Recent lifestyle changes have increased gastric issues in many people, particularly young adults. PPIs are commonly used to address these symptoms. Their over-the-counter availability and the immediate symptom relief have resulted in their use. However, both the abrupt discontinuation and the prolonged use of PPIs can lead to a range of side effects and complications. It is crucial to avoid sudden discontinuation of PPIs, especially in long-term users, and strategic discontinuation should be adopted to avoid rebound acid hypersecretion. Homoeopathic medicines help treat and prevent numerous diseases. They can also assist in avoiding the withdrawal symptoms of discontinuing PPIs.

The main aim of this study is to determine the effectiveness of homeopathic medicines for patients on proton pump inhibitors for gastric complaints. The primary objective is to reduce the intensity of gastric symptoms seen in patients who are on proton pump inhibitors. The secondary objective is to reduce the use of PPI by using homoeopathic medicines. The hypothesis tested was to know if homoeopathic medicines are effective in patients with gastric complaints who are on proton pump inhibitors (there is a significant difference between GIQLI scores before and after treatment). The outcome assessment to test the hypothesis was based on the before and after treatment scores of the Gastro-Intestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) score.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was carried out at Bharati Vidyapeeth Medical Foundation Homoeopathic Hospital, OPD of the Department of Practice of Medicine. A total of 30 patients (males and females) with age groups between 18 to 75 years, who are previously diagnosed with gastric conditions like GERD, Gastritis, ulcers, reflux oesophagitis etc, or have Gastric complaints and using PPIs 3-5 times/week for more than 4-8 weeks to reduce their symptoms were enrolled in the study. The case-taking was done by standard case-taking proforma as per homoeopathic principles. Homepath Zomeo software was used for the repertorization of the cases. The Gastrointestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) was used as the assessment tool. The score was taken during the first visit, third follow-up and last(fifth) follow-up. Differences between the scores taken in the first and last follow-ups are used for the outcome assessment.

Ethics :

Ethical committee approval was availed.

Guidelines by ICMR (Indian Council of Medical Research), and ICH (International Council for

Harmonization) are followed.

Data was collected by proper method and will be processed in standard format with the following aspects.

Patients were selected according to the case definition.

Details of the study work are explained to the patient.

The patient's information sheet form was formed and filled up. And their informed consent was taken.

Standardized case records were prepared and maintained of individual patients and standardized follow-up sheets were prepared and maintained regularly.

Records of all cases in detail as per standardized case Performa has maintained along with follow-ups.

The total research project was submitted to the ethical committee

Nosological diagnosis is done after clinical study

The declaration was given that the drugs used were not harmful to human beings, said the remedy is already available in the homoeopathic literature, was well proven on healthy human beings is harmless and has no side effects.

STUDY DESIGN:

SITE OF THE STUDY: The study was carried out at Bharati Vidyapeeth Medical Foundation Homoeopathic Hospital, OPD of the Department of Practice of Medicine.

CASE DEFINITION: Persons who are presenting with Gastric complaints and using Proton Pump Inhibitors, 3-5 times/week for more than 4-8 weeks to reduce their symptoms with age groups between 18 to 75 years of age and both sexes were included in the study.

ALLOCATION: Non-randomized, Individualistic study.

END POINT: Effectiveness.

BLINDING: Open.

SAMPLE SIZE: 30

DURATION OF STUDY: study was conducted for 18 months

SELECTION OF SAMPLE: Persons as per the case definition were selected under the guidance of the respected Guide of the practice of medicine.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. All the Patients who fit the case definition.
2. Patients of both sexes.
3. Patients with age groups between 18 years and 75 years.
4. Patients without any major systemic complications.
5. Patients willing to participate in the study and give informed consent.
6. Patients who comply with the study procedures.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patients who don't fit the case definition.

Patients under the age of 18 years.

Patients above the age of 75 years.

Patients with complications of GERD, bleeding ulcers, Zollinger-Ellison syndrome and major systemic complaints.

Patients who require surgical intervention.

Patients who don't consent to the study.

INTERVENTION: Individualistic homoeopathic medicines.

SELECTION OF THE REMEDY: After detailed case-taking and physical examination, totality was formed and remedy selection was done according to symptom similarity.

SELECTION OF TOOLS

Gastro-Intestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI)

The GIQLI is a 36-item GI-specific HRQL instrument designed to assess HRQL in clinical practice and clinical trials of patients with GI disorders. The GIQLI has five subscales (GI Symptoms, Emotion, Physical Function, Social Function, and Medical Treatment) and a Total Score. Higher scores represent better HRQL; sub-scores range from 0–4 while the total score ranges from 0–144.⁽²⁾ Calculation of the

score: most desirable option: 4 points least desirable option: 0 points GIQLI score: sum of the points.⁽³⁾

Homepath Zomeo software

Homepath Zomeo software was used for the repertorization of the cases.

DRUG DISPENSING: Remedies are given in globules (sucrose) form.

DOSE OF DRUG: Patients are advised to take the medicine once a day.

DRUG ADMINISTRATION: Administered through oral route. The first dose will be given in front of the physician & further doses will be given 6 pills X BD for 7 Days. Repetition of dose will be done as per the need of the patient.

BRIEF OF PROCEDURES:

Sample was selected based on the case definition.

Detailed case-taking was conducted as per the standard proforma.

Patients were assessed based on the Gastro-Intestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI).

All the symptoms were noted and evaluation was done.

Selection of remedy: The remedy was selected based on symptom similarity and by repertorization.

OUTCOME ASSESSMENT:

The Gastrointestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) was used as the assessment tool. The score was taken during the first visit, third follow-up and last(fifth) follow-up. Differences between the scores taken in the first and last follow-ups are used for the outcome assessment.

Follow-up criteria- Duration of follow-up -once in 7 days.

CRITERIA FOR ASSESSMENT:

The Gastrointestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) was used for assessment of improvement of the patients Before and After Treatment.

Marked improvement: when there is more than 75% disappearance of the symptoms.

Moderate improvement: when the patient has symptomatic relief with 50-75% reduction of the complaints.

Mild improvement: when the patient has symptomatic relief with less than 50% reduction of the complaints.

No improvement: No response seen after treatment.

Worse: Aggravation of subjective and objective symptoms.

Dropped out: 5 dropouts have been seen due to the patient opting out of the study due to transfers or the attending physician does not want to keep the patient under study for any valid reason.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

A specially designed Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and Microsoft Word document were sent for data extraction. The inference was subjected to statistical analysis based on the score of The Gastrointestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI). A registered statistician did the statistical analysis. A paired t-test was used for the descriptive statistical analysis of the GIQLI score before and after the intervention. **mean ± standard deviation** was used for the GIQLI score difference between after and before the treatment to show the improvement level. **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** was used to know the difference in score before and after treatment for the symptoms; Pain, Bloating, Regurgitation, and Heartburn.

RESULTS:

The effectiveness of homoeopathic remedies in the long-term management of gastrointestinal disorders caused by PPI use has been assessed in this clinical study. The study is carried out in the OPD of the Department of Practice of Medicine BVDU Homoeopathic Medical College. The maximum amount of time for the participants in the study is 18 months. These patients' data, which were used in this study, provided the basis for statistical analysis. The sample size was 30 and patients belonged to age groups between 18- and 75-years age. Among them 16.67% of the patients had an age between 18-25 years, 36.67% of the patients had an age between 25-35 years, 26.67% had an age between 35-45 years the remaining 20% were the patients that are above 45 years in this study. 50% of patients were females and 50% were males in the study.

Gastro-Intestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) SCORE ANALYSIS:

The main aim and primary objective were to reduce the intensity of gastric symptoms that are seen in patients who are on proton pump inhibitors. Outcome assessment is done based on the difference between initial and final scores. Data on Gastro-Intestinal Quality of Life Index- scores were studied before and after treatment. A paired t-test was applied to the GIQLI score. Here average GIQLI Score was compared before and after treatment. Before the intervention of treatment, the average GIQLI score was $100.46 + 11.21$ (mean \pm SD) and after the intervention, the average GIQLI score was $127.66 + 9.99$ (mean \pm SD). 95% CI for the mean difference is (-30.99, -23.40). The t-statistic value was -14.68 and the significant p-value of 0.00*. It concludes that there was a significant difference in the average GIQLI score, before and after treatment showing Homoeopathic medicines are effective in patients with gastric complaints who are on proton pump inhibitors.

GIQLI Score	N	GIQLI Score Mean+ SD	T Statistic Value	P-Value
Before treatment	30	100.46 + 11.21	T-stat -14.68	0.00*
After treatment	30	127.66 + 9.99		
95% CI for the mean difference		(-30.99, -23.40)		

P Value <0.05, Considered to be statistically significant.

Table 1: Paired t-test and Descriptive statistics of the GIQLI score before and after the intervention.

Figure 1: Bar diagram representing the Mean + SD of GIQLI Score.

Distribution of patients according to the quality of life before and after the intervention:

This study also examines the mental aspect and the quality of life of patients. It measures how much difficulty they have in doing their work, running their household, or socializing with others. After the treatment 36.67% of the patients had a marked improvement, 40% of patients showed a moderate level of improvement, whereas 20% of patients had a mild improvement. Only 3.33% of patients had no improvement. **mean \pm standard deviation** of the GIQLI score difference between after and before the treatment. For patients with marked improvement, the average GIQLI difference was 36.82 ± 5.13 . For patients with moderate improvement, the average GIQLI difference was 26.75 ± 3.22 . Whereas for patients with mild improvement, the average GIQLI difference was 14.33 ± 3.44 .

Level of Improvement	No. of Patients	Percentage
Marked	11	36.67%
Moderate	12	40.00%
Mild	6	20.00%
No improvement	1	3.33%

Table 2: Distribution of patients by Improvement Level.

Figure 2: Bar diagram representing the Mean ± SD of GIQLI Score difference

Remedy-wise distribution of the patients:

During the study among 30 patients, Nux-Vomica was given to 23.33% of patients. Phosphorus was given to 20% of patients. Each of Bryonia and Argentum nitricum was given to 13.33% of patients. Each of Pulsatilla, Lycopodium, and Arsenicum album was prescribed to 10% of patients. Among patients treated with Bryonia and Argentum nitricum, 75% had moderate improvement and the remaining 25% showed mild improvement. Among patients treated with pulsatilla Arsenicum album and Lycopodium, 66.7% had marked improvement, and the remaining 33.3% showed moderate improvement. When patients received Nux Vomica, 42.9% had marked improvement. About 28.6% experienced moderate improvement, while the other 28.6% reported mild improvement in their gastric complaints. For patients treated with Phosphorus 50% experienced marked improvement, 33.3% showed moderate improvement and the remaining 16.7% had mild improvement in gastric complaints.

REMEDY	Number of patients	Percentage
Argentum nitricum	4	13.33%
Arsenicum album	3	10.00%
Bryonia	4	13.33%
Lycopodium	3	10.00%
Nux Vomica	7	23.33%
Phosphorus	6	20.00%
Pulsatilla	3	10.00%

Table 3: Remedy-wise distribution of patients.

Figure 3: Bar diagram representing the Remedy-wise distribution of patients by level of improvement

Difference in the symptom Score before and after treatment.

The study also shows that there is a significant difference between the symptom score which is taken before and after the treatment. For the hypothesis, “The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test” was used to test.

Pain: Prior to treatment, the median Pain score was 1 (IQR: 1), indicating that patients commonly

experienced pain most of the time. Post-treatment, there was a significant increase in the median Pain score to 4 (IQR: 1), suggesting a substantial reduction in pain severity. On average, patients reported no more pain following treatment. **Bloating:** There was a notable increase in the median score from 1 (IQR: 1) to 3(IQR: 0), suggesting a substantial reduction in bloating symptoms. **Regurgitation:** The median score increased from 1 (IQR: 0.25) to 3 (IQR: 0), indicating a significant decrease in regurgitation frequency. **Heartburn:** The median score increased from 2 (IQR: 3) to 4 (IQR: 1), reflecting a significant reduction in heartburn occurrences.

Based on these findings of the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, we rejected the null hypothesis for all symptoms. We conclude that there is a statistically significant improvement in Pain, Bloating, Regurgitation, and Heartburn scores after treatment, enhancing patients' quality of life. The results showed a significant difference between the symptom score before and after treatment, the test statistic for pain score was $Z=-4.615$ with a p-value of 0.00. Similarly, Bloating, Regurgitation, and heartburn score before and after treatment were studied. Corresponding observed z-statistic values were -4.636, -4.934 and -4.05 respectively. The corresponding p-values were <0.01 , statistically highly significant. Based on these findings, the study also concluded that there is a statistically significant improvement in Pain, Bloating, Regurgitation, and Heartburn scores after treatment, enhancing patients' quality of life.

Variable	Ranks	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Test statistic and P-value
Pain score difference	Negative	0.00	0.00	$Z = -4.615$
	Positive	14.00	378.00	P-value =0.00**
Bloating score difference	Negative	0.00	0.00	$Z= -4.636$
	Positive	13.50	351.00	P-value =0.00**
Regurgitation score difference	Negative	3.50	3.50	$Z=-4.934$
	Positive	15.41	431.50	P-value =0.00**
Heartburn score difference	Negative	0.00	0.00	$Z=-4.058$
	Positive	10.50	210.00	P-value =0.00**

Table 4: **Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test** for Pain, Bloating, Regurgitation, Heartburn score before and after treatment **: Highly Significant Difference, p-value **: highly significant (<0.01). Negative ranks were calculated for Symptom score after treatment $<$ symptom score before treatment. Positive ranks were calculated for Symptom score after treatment $>$ Symptom score before treatment.

Symptom	N	Mean \pm Sd	Minimum	Median (IQR)	Maximum	
Pain score	Before treatment	30	1.63 \pm 0.89	1	1(1)	4
	After treatment	30	3.63 \pm 0.72	1	4(1)	4
Bloating score	Before treatment	30	1.57 \pm 0.82	0	1(1)	3
	After treatment	30	3.00 \pm 0.37	2	3(0)	4
Regurgitation score	Before treatment	30	1.30 \pm 0.65	1	1(0.25)	4
	After treatment	30	2.97 \pm 0.41	1	3(0)	4
Heartburn score	Before treatment	30	2.23 \pm 1.28	1	2(3)	4
	After treatment	30	3.47 \pm 0.68	1	4(1)	4

IQR: (difference between 3rd quartile and 1st quartile)

Table 5: Descriptive statistics of Pain, Bloating, Regurgitation, Heartburn score before and after treatment

Figure 4: Median score of symptoms before and after treatment.

Table 5 and Figure 4 present the descriptive statistics for scores related to Pain, Bloating, Regurgitation, and Heartburn before and after treatment. The scoring system is as follows: 0 indicates constant symptoms, 1 denotes symptoms occurring most of the time, 2 represents symptoms occurring some of the time, 3 suggests symptoms occurring a little amount of time, and 4 signifies no symptoms.

Discussion:

The study conducted at BVDU Homoeopathic Medical College aimed to determine the effectiveness of homoeopathic medicines in managing gastrointestinal disorders caused by proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) in gastric complaints. The sample size was 30 patients aged 18-75 years, with 16.67% aged between 18-25 years, 36.67% aged between 25-35 years, 26.67% aged between 35-45 years, and 20% aged above 45 years. The Gastro-Intestinal Quality of Life Index (GIQLI) score was analysed before and after treatment, showing a significant difference in the average GIQLI score before and after treatment. The study also examined the mind symptoms and quality of life of patients, measuring their difficulty in work, household, or socializing. After treatment, 36.67% of patients showed marked improvement, 40% showed moderate improvement, and 20% had mild improvement. Only 3.33% of patients had no improvement. Remedy-wise distribution of patients was also examined. Nux-Vomica was given to 23.33% of patients, Phosphorus to 20%, Bryonia and Argentum nitricum to 13.33%, Pulsatilla, Lycopodium, and Arsenicum album to 10%. Among patients treated with Bryonia and Argentum nitricum, 75% showed moderate improvement, while 66.7% showed marked improvement. For Nux Vomica, 42.9% experienced marked improvement, 28.6% showed moderate improvement, and 28.6% had mild improvement. For Phosphorus, 50% experienced marked improvement, 33.3% showed moderate improvement, and 16.7% had mild improvement. The results also showed a significant difference between the symptom score before and after treatment. There is a significant improvement in Pain, Bloating, Regurgitation, and Heartburn scores after treatment, enhancing patients' quality of life. In conclusion, the study shows that Homoeopathic medicines are effective in managing gastrointestinal disorders caused by PPI use.

CONCLUSION:

Homoeopathic remedies have demonstrated substantial effectiveness in treating gastric symptoms, indicating that they are effective in patients with gastric complaints who are on PPIs.

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